

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ISONIAZID BY USING RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

Every day many chromatography's face the need to develop a high- performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method. This review describes the systematic procedures for developing an HPLC method, based on the best information available. HPLC method development involves several essential steps: sample pretreatment, detection of sample bands, choosing separation conditions, quantitation and method validation. HPLC is an analytical tool which is able to detect, separate and quantify the drug, its various impurities and drug related degradates that can form on the synthesis or storage. It also includes the understanding of chemistry of drug substance and improves the development of analytical method. Validation is to performed to determine the limits of allowed variability for the conditions needed to run the method. This article describes strategies & an issues comes in development

of a HPLC method development & validation.

KEYWORDS: DL: Detection Limit; QL: Quantitation Limit.

INTRODUCTION

Chromatography is relatively a new technique which was first invented by M.TSWETT, a botanist in 1906 in Warsaw. In that year, he was successful in doing the separation of chlorophyll, xanthophyll, and other colored substance by percolating vegetable extract through a column of calcium carbonate. The calcium carbonate column act as an adsorbent and different substance got absorbed to different extent and this gives rise to colour bands at

different positions, on column. termed this system of color bands as the chromatogram and the method as chromatography after the Greek words chroma and grapho meaning colour and writing respectively. However, in majority of chromatographic procedures no coloured products are formed and the term is misnomer. Recovery of separated substance by a continuous flow of the mobile phase; the method being called elution.

Types of chromatography

In chromatography, the stationary phase may be a liquid or a solid and the mobile phase may be a liquid or gas. Depending on the stationary phase and the mobile phase used, separation occurs because of combination of two or more factors such as rate of migration, capillary action, extent of adsorption. chromatographic methods can be classified on the basis of stationary phase and mobile phase.^[1]

1. Column chromatography.
2. Partition chromatography.
3. Paper chromatography.
4. Thin layer chromatography(TLC).
5. Gas -liquid chromatography(GLC).
6. Gas -solid chromatography(GSC).

METHODOLOGY

A HPLC method was developed for the estimation of isoniazid in the tablet dosage form [300mg]. By selecting various chromatographic conditions like retention time, wavelength, column, determination of isocratic elution, mobile phase and diluents. A HPLC method was developed for the estimation of isoniazid in the tablet dosage form [300mg]. By selecting various chromatographic conditions like retention time, wavelength, column, determination of isocratic elution, mobile phase and diluents.

The following chromatographic conditions were fixed initially to improve the separation of isoniazid.

Mode of operation	: Isocratic system
Stationary phase	: C ₁₈ Column (150 mm x 4.6 mm), 5µm particle size
Mobile phase	: Methanol: Phosphate buffer pH 2.5
Ratio	: 50:50% v/v
Detection wavelength	: 254 nm
Flow rate	: 1 ml/min

Temperature :Ambient(27°c) Sample volume :20µml.

The mobile phase was allowed to run for 7 minutes to record a steady base line. Isoniazid drug solution was injected and chromatogram was recorded. It was observed the drug was eluted at 6.176. Hence the different ratios of mobile phase were tried to reduce the retention time of isoniazid.^[2]

Effect of Composition and ratio of mobile phase: The mobile phases like Methanol, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer were used in the study. Phosphate buffer was tried with Methanol and Acetonitrile. The different ratios of mobile phase tried were 50:50, 55:45, 45:55, 30:70, and 60:40 v/v. By changing the composition of mobile phase, these ratios were studied. Phosphate buffer with Acetonitrile shows poor baseline and Phosphate buffer with Methanol shows good separation with 55:45% v/v.

Effect of pH of mobile phase: The different pH solutions were tried i.e. 2.5, 3.0 with methanol and phosphate buffer in the ratio 45:55% v/v and the chromatograms were recorded. When comparing the chromatogram obtained for the different pH solutions, at pH 3.0, the peak was good than pH solution 2.5.

Effect of flow rate on separation: Different flow rate like 0.9 ml/min and 1 ml/min were tried with methanol and phosphate buffer. In 1ml/min the chromatogram shows good separation than 0.9 ml/min. Hence Methanol and Phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) in the ratio of 55:45% v/v with 1 ml/min flow rate was used for further studies.

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions: The following parameters were used for RP-HPLC analysis of isoniazid

Mode of operation: Isocratic system.

Stationary phase: C18 Column (150 mm x 4.6 mm i.d., 5µ)

Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer pH 3.0: Methanol

Ratio: 55:45 % v/v

Detection wavelength: 240-255nm

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Temperature: Ambient Sample volume: 20µl.

Preparation of Phosphate buffer: Weigh 7.0 grams of Potassium dihydrogen Phosphate into a 1000 ml beaker. dissolve and diluted to 1000 ml with HPLC water. Adjusted the pH to 3.0

with ortho phosphoric acid.

Preparation of mobile phase: Mix a mixture of above buffer 450 ml (55%) and 550 ml of Methanol HPLC (45%) and degas in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.45 μ filter.

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Isoniazid into a 10 ml volumetric flask add about 7 ml of mobile phase and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the mobile phase. The solution was observed to contain 1000 μ g/ml.

Preparation of Sample solution: Weigh 10 Isoniazid tablets and calculate the average weight. Accurately weigh and transfer the sample equivalent to 10 mg of Isoniazid into a 10ml volumetric flask.

System suitability: System suitability test should be carried out to verify that the analytical system is working properly and can give accurate and precise results. Standard solutions were prepared as per the test method and injected into the chromatographic system. The system suitability parameters were evaluated from tailing factor, retention times and theoretical plates of standard chromatograms. Standard solution preparations were injected five times into the chromatograph and retention times were recorded.^[3]

Precision: The precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple sampling of homogeneous sample. The precision of analytical method is usually expressed as the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (coefficient of variation) of series of measurements. Pipette out 0.3 ml of the stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with mobile phase. Mix well and filter through 0.45 μ m filter. The solution was observed to contain 30 μ g/ml. The solution was injected for five times and measures the area in HPLC.

Detection limit and quantitation limit (lod and loq): The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value and the quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The detection limit and the quantitation limit can be calculated based on the Standard Deviation of the Response and the Slope. The

Detection Limit (DL) may be expressed as: $DL = 3.3F / S$. The Quantitation Limit (QL) may be expressed as: $QL = 10F / S$

Where,

F = Residual Standard deviation of the response,

S = Slope of the calibration curve.

Procedure.

Limit of detection: Pipette out 0.1 ml of the stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with mobile phase. Mix well and filter through 0.45 μ m filter. The solution was observed to contain 10 μ g / m l Pipette 1ml of 10 μ g / m l solution into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with mobile phase. Further pipette 0.09 ml solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to mark mobile phase.

Limit of quantification: Pipette out 0.1 ml of the stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with mobile phase. Mix well and filter through 0.45 μ m filter. The solution was observed to contain 10 μ g / m l Pipette I ml of 10 μ g / m l solution into a 10 ml of volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with mobile phase. Further pipette 0.03 ml solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to mark mobile phase.^[4]

Linearity: The linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly, or by a well-defined mathematical transformation, proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range. Linearity was performed in the range of LOQ to 200% of impurity level. Prepared the standard solution in the following range and injected into the chromatograph.

Preparation of calibration graph: In this method, the aliquots of stock solution of Isoniazid (0.1-0.5 ml of 1000 μ g/ml) were transferred into five 10 ml volumetric flask and make up to the mark with mobile phase. A solution contains 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μ g/ml of Isoniazid in mobile phase. The solutions were injected and the chromatograms were recorded at 218 nm. It was found that the above concentration range was linear with the concentration range of 10-50 μ g/ml. The peak area was plotted against concentration and the calibration curve was constructed.

Accuracy: The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and

the value found. The study was performed by making three different standard concentrations 50%, 100% and 150% of known amounts of studied drugs. Finally, the final volume made up with solvent (mobile phase) and mixed well. The resulting mixtures were analyzed by the proposed HPLC method. The excellent mean recoveries and standard deviation suggests good accuracy results of the proposed method.^[5]

CONCLUSION

The solution of 9 µg/ml of Isoniazid in mobile phase (Methanol and Phosphate buffer pH 3.0 in the ratio of 45:55% v/v) was prepared and the solution scanned in the UV region. At 218 nm the drug showed maximum absorbance. Blank was run with the help of Methanol and Phosphate buffer in the ratio of 55:45% v/v. The separation was first tried with acetonitrile and phosphate buffer. By keeping pH (3.0) and flow rate (0.5 ml/min) as constant, and by changing the mobile phase ratio like 50:50, 60:40, 30:70% v/v three trials were performed. It shows poor baseline and high retention time. Then the separation was tried with methanol and phosphate buffer. By keeping pH (2.5) and flow rate 0.5 ml/min constant three trials were performed and it shows poor baseline and high retention time. Then the separation was tried with the same by changing flow rate from 0.5-0.6 ml/min and by changing the mobile phase composition. With methanol and phosphate buffer in the ratio 45:55% v/v, it shows good separation. With the optimized chromatographic conditions, stock solutions of Isoniazid were prepared by using mobile phase (phosphate buffer pH 3.0 and methanol in the ratio 55:45% v/v) and various concentrations were prepared in the range of 10-50 µg/ml and injected individually. The limit of detection was found to be 0.027 µg/ml and the limit of quantification was found to be 0.09 µg/ml. The percentage purity of the Isoniazid was found to be 100.07%. The percentage recovery of Isoniazid at 50%, 100% and 150% levels was found to be 101.8%, 101.4% and 101.6% respectively and are within the limits. 30 µg/ml solution of Isoniazid was prepared from the stock solution and injected five times and the areas of five injections were recorded in HPLC. The RSD was found to be 0.26. It shows the intermediate precision is within the specified limit. All the above parameters combined with the simplicity and ease of operation ensures that the application of proposed method in the assay of drug in pharmaceutical dosage form. Hence the RP-HPLC method may be applied for the estimation of Isoniazid.

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